

E-content development for Natrinai resource in ta.Wikisource

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Abstract

The scheme Wiki source is widely being used across 72 Languages. Among this Tamil Wiki source is an online library scheme which belongs to the Wikimedia Trust. This serves as the e- library sharing the license of the original sources of books. Anyone interested in this scheme can enrol themselves and shall upload, make corrections and post suggestions on updating the books. More than 2468 Tamil books are made available to the users through this Tamil Wiki source scheme. The collection spans above 3.5 lakhs pages comprising various books from Sangam Literature, Bhakti Literature, Literature from countryside (Folk Literature or Folklore), History, Science, Travelogues and History of Life. It can be noted that the data encircling the Literature from ancient Tamil culture which deals with the antiquity of Tamil Language is very minimal. It is evident from the fact that "Natrinai " has only one authentic source for reference, as secondary sources and as any data associated with it. The data that is available to us has no proper substantiation on the source of the data available. Also there arises a question on the minimal attribution to the number of the books associated with Natrinai. What would be the best possible solution to this. Should we not think about its development? Hence through his study it is mandated on the importance of identifying at least the free licensed books from the Wiki source. It is the duty of the Volunteers. This study brings these key notes to the Limelight. This can be achieved by accumulating all the scarce information that are available form publishing houses and other significant centres that could result in finding the gap in updating the information about a particular book and make it notable. Studies like this play a pivotal role in fetching Linguistic Data and information for the sake of enhancing one's knowledge of Language and Linguistic grounds. This accumulation of information paves the way for the future studies on cognitive technology or in the research on the nature of Languages in the days to come. Hence, this study deals with the list of books and sources that are associated with Natrinai and are not available in Wiki source platform and the significance of updating those sources in the platform.

Keywords: Wikisource, Natrinai, Source, version.

Introduction

Wiki source opened the Window of wisdom enabling the access to E- content based in Tamil language. This is an ardent responsibility of the researchers and enthusiasts pertaining to Tamil Language and Literature to employ their labour to develop the resources available for Tamil Language. Since the days of Tholkaapiyam, and ranging to various greats of literature have been treasured for centuries together and in a similar way it is the need of the hour to safeguard the available resources through the medium of internet as E- media. Stressing on this fact, this study delves upon the significance of structuring the resources for Natrinai on the historical basis of Tamil Literature and the guidelines on uploading the same in the E-platform of Wiki source.

Natrinai and its Uniqueness

Natrinai is a part of Sangam Literature and has its place in the literary text of EttuThogai which is a collection of songs based on Akam porul. Natrinai comprises 400 poems differing in length between 9 and 12 lines respectively. Among the 400 poems, poem no 234 is not found [15].

- Important text on subjective Poetry
- Portrays various stages of love in a vivid manner
- Equipped with rich literary devices like Iraicci, Metaphor and Ullurai
- Vital documentation in understanding the culture and society of its time. [15]

Love in Natrinai

Natrinai being a collection of Subjective poetry is flooded with information giving vantage perspective on Love. The Poetic greats of the age have skilfully carved the innate feelings of Love at various stages and depicted in their poetry.

Initial stages of Love

Natrinai beholds a number of poetries on the initial stages of the happiness of Love. The initial stage were the lovers meet one another and fall in love; the stage where lovers live with instances of their first meeting relishing their cherished moments of seeing their loved one and reluctant patience and longingness in waiting to see each other. [15]

Blossoming Stage in Love

One of the important stages in the blossoming of Love is separation. This also has an inherent part in Natrinai. The stage of separation of lovers; stage of suffering due to the separation; stage of reminiscence of their happy days during their separation and the feeling of missing each other is eloquently penned as poems.

Final Stage of Love

Poems about the profound state of love where the lovers join together in harmony is also found in Natrinai. The stage where the lovers hold hands and join together; the stage

where they express their love towards each other after their joining; the optimistic ideology on the happy life they will be leading once after they join with each other are represented in the poems of Natrinai.

Significance of Literary Device in Natrinai

Natrinai is Equipped with rich literary devices like Iraicci, Metaphor and Ullurai.

- Simile

Natrinai is filled with extraordinary comparisons throughout the text. Great comparisons of Love with that of natural elements like Birds, flowers, Moon, stars make the poems exceptional.

- Metaphor

Metaphor is signifying one aspect with something else. The poems of Natrinai are rich in metaphorical references. The feeling of Love is signified with association of flowers, birds, moon and stars.

- Imagery

Imagery is bringing an object to the readers by kindling their sensory with description on the shape, structure, colour and taste. One can sense exquisite use of imagery in the poems of Natrinai. The expression of love by associating it with the taste, shape, structure and colour of flowers, birds, moon and stars makes the poem admiringly beautiful.

It is the need of the hour to upgrade such a important literary work. In order levy weightage of this very fact some of important facets on Natrinai as provided by Google Bard is furnished here. Also, when the user uses the keyword “Natrinaiyin Olaisuvadigal” to search in Google Bard, the responses are as follows.

The response from Google Bard for “Natrinaiyin Olaisuvadigal”- A Note

The Palm leaf manuscripts of Natrinai can be seen in different places including

- Educational Institutions
 - Library of Chennai University
 - Library of Madurai Kamaraj University
 - Library of Trichi University
 - Library of Madurai Tamil Sangam
- Temples
 - Library of Thivarur Panjavarneshwara Temple
 - Library of Thiruvannamali Annamalaitar Temple
 - Library of Thirunelveli Vadamalaiyar Temple
- Personal Collections

Significance of Palm leaf manuscripts of Natrinai

- It serves as evidence of the fact that those were written during the Sangam age.
- It is an important documentation in understanding the authenticity of the Literature.
- It signifies the antiquity and rich cultural, heritage and sound knowledge in literacy of Tamil Language.

Safeguarding the Palm leaf manuscripts of Natrinai

The Palm leaf Manuscripts of Natrinai accounts for a very rare and valuable aspect. Henceforth it is mandated to safeguard it. The following measures are taken in safeguarding it.

- The Maintenance of these is handled with utmost care.
- They are placed at distance out of hand reach hence limiting the physical access.
- They are continuously monitored and are always under surveillance.

The Palm leaf manuscripts of Natrinai is a treasured wealth and safeguarding it becomes a crucial part in safeguarding Tamil Language.

Natrinai in Webs

The availability of Natrinai as in print media is very commendable and no other form the same shall be found in web is the bitter truth which unravelled during this study. The simplest form of explanations for Natrinai in E- media and translations including etymological texts are available on the web. Tamil Online Educational forum facilitates the explanation of Pinnathoorar in the form of print medium. With Natrinai as primary source there are many notes regarding the statements along with a note on the author available in the websites. But only 12 poems are available on the Wiki source platform.

This is not just the status of Natrinai, also other tamil literary works of Ethhi Thogai including Kurunthogai, Pathitru Pathu, Pari padal along with ancient tamil classical books, the lateral books literature and grammar in tamil language have very minimal sources in Wiki source platform. Uploading these important texts in the E- media Wiki source would be the compelling step forward. This is the important work of converting the manuscripts to print media for longevity and transferring that in turn into E- content for accessibility across the globe is the significance of this step.

Natrinai – The Text and Editions

Among the many who contributed in writing the explanations and secondary sources on Natrinai Pinathoorar. A. Narayanasamy Iyer and Narrator Avvai Su. Duraisami pillai are highly notable. The text on Natrinai by Pinathoorar was published in 1915. It would be the right way to Homage to Pinathoorar by digitising the texts of Natrinai in Wiki source and acknowledge his labour in converting Natrinai to print media before days of Independence.

Honoured with the title Narrator, Avvai Su. Duraisami has written detailed textual notes

on various important Tami literary texts including Natrinai, Aingurunooru, Pathitrupathu and Purananooru. The texts of Avvai. Su. Duraisami is already nationalised. In his text, he has explained the setting of Natrinai is narrated as that of a story.

Puliyoorkesigan has written explanations based on the pre existing explanations from the predecessors for the texts of Sangam Literature, Pathinen Keezhkanankku. His texts also fall under the list of books which were nationalised.

Among the three, the works of Puliyoorkesigan are updated in Wiki source and the works of the other two shall also be uploaded in the platform. This shall ensure in strengthening the resources on Natrinai in the E- platform as the textual expertise of these renowned writers have its own essence of uniqueness offering vantage perspective to the texts.

Pinnathoorar Text: Natrinai

The text of Pinnathoorar on Natrinai can be equated to an exclusive encyclopedia of Natrinai. His texts comprise information on Poets, hidden meanings, metaphorical references, uses, statements of individuals on notes, explanations and etymology of the texts pertaining to Natrinai and are segregated under different traits. These factors make his works a highly treasurable source on understanding Natrinai. By uploading this treasured text in Wiki source helps in achieving greater purpose of the text and form the basis of strengthening the e-content of Natrinai.

Narrator's Text: Residence and Epigraphy

The text of Narrator Avvai Su. Duraisamy holds information on historical information, Nativity of poets, epigraphical evidence on the places covered in the book. The citations of Ancient Tamil names of the ancestors, name of the places are detailed with epigraphical evidence in his work. Having such an affluent text in Wikki source makes it important not only for Natrinai but also serves useful to readers and scholars pertaining to names of ancient people and places.

While updating his text in Wiki source, enabling the click option on Names of location, towns, and peoples can also improve the data on Natrinai along with Tamil Language in general.

Puliyoor Kesigan' Text: 20th Century Linguistics

Puliyoor Kesigan's text differs from the text of the other two on the linguistic basis of the 20th century. Also, his texts put forth the important information from the poem in the beginning of the poem, thus making it unique. This text also details the syllables of the poems used and defines it by segregating it on syllables for better understanding.

Murray Version: Natrinai Sources

“This version of Natrinai published in 1957 was work done by Murray S. Rajam along with team comprising Vaiyaburi Pillai and other publishers who compared the pre existing

texts and published this new version". Vaiyaburi pillai was one of leading members who were part of this compilation. No meter was followed and this version was drafted in such a way to make it available for everyone to have it in a more readable and much simpler form. Words are separated on the basis of needed ensuring easy readability. Hence uploading this version will enable everyone to read Natrinai from Wiki source.

Perumazhai Pulavar Text:

Perumazhai Pulavar Po. Ve. Somasundaranar is one of the important writers of the 21st century. He has written detailed texts explaining the books of Sangam Literature in Contemporary language. He has also contributed to Pinathoorar text's later editions by adding explanations wherever needed. This work was published by Saiva Sidhanth Publishing corporation. Nationalising the works of Perumazhai Poet is brought to the forefront in recent times. Once after Nationalising, his works shall also be updated in Wiki source.

Literary Treasure: Feast of Natrinai

Despite concentrating on various versions, text and sources of Natrinai, "Natrinai Virundhu" (Feast of Natrinai) written by Ka. Govindan collectively compiles all the important information from Natrinai and presents it to the readers in the form of essays. This work is also Nationalised. While the typography of this work in Wiki source is completed, the proof reading of the same is pending.

Natrinai in Wiki Source

Wiki source contains five books associated with Natrinai. Of which four books are available with the original source (primary source) and the other is available only as a textual documentation without its original source. It was only on December 30, 2023 that a separate section comprising the five books of Natrinai was found and made available. Also, the necessity of updating can be understood from the above cited information. The process and guidelines of upgrading text that are about to be written in the future will also have to be concentrated.

Improving Tabulation of Natrinai

This study also emphasises on spreading awareness on the importance of not limiting the documents associated with Natrinai within the purview of print media.

The detailing on the tabulation of documents on Natrinai shall be as follows.

- Natrinai in Palm Leaf Manuscripts
 - Primary Source of the Manuscripts
 - Secondary Source of the Manuscripts
- Natrinai as printed books
 - Primary text
 - Secondary texts

- Older Texts
- Textuality
- Contemporary text
- Research books (Theses)
 - Comparison of Indian languages
 - Comparison of Foreign languages
 - Comparison of Dravidian languages
 - Comparison within Tamil language, literature and Grammar text
- Translational Studies

This way of tabulation or arrangement will prove effective to any period in time. An attempt to arrange a table shall be made. We should also remember the tabulation method of Mu. Va while doing this, as his explanation says,

“Tamil literary history shall be distinguished in different ways where people from other linguistic backgrounds should be able to understand the Literary works in Tamil and such should be the arrangement made and prepared as follows.

Old Age

- Sangam Literature: From 500.B. C to 200 AD comprising of Agam and Puram
- Moral Literature: From 100 A. D to 500 AD comprising of Thirukkural, Kaarnaarpathu and also including the books of venba muthollayiram
- Dual Epics: From 100 AD to 500 AD
- Includes Silapathikaram, Manimekalai, etc.

Medieval Age

- Bhakthi Literature: From 600 AD to 900 comprising the poems and songs of Naayanmaars and Aazhvaars.
- Diverse Books: 700 AD to 1300
- Epics: From 500 AD to 1200 AD composed of Jain and Buddhist books like Perumkadhai, Seevaga Sindhamani, also includes the works of Sekkizhar, Avvaiyaar and Ula Barani Pillai Tamil.
- Grammar books such as Irayanar Kalaviyal etc.
- Textbooks: From 1200 AD to 1500 AD comprising Ilampooranaar and Perasiriyar.
- Vaishnava explanatory books, Saiva Siddhanta books, short books and Thani Padalgal
- Puranic Literature: From 1500 AD to 1800 AD comprising Puranas, Thalapuranas, Islamic Literature, Christian Literature from Veeramamunivar and the development of

Prose works.

Nineteenth Century:

- Including Christian Literature, Ramalinganaar, Vedhanayagar, development of Novel and Essays.

Present Age:

- Christian Literature:
- Bharathi, Kalki, Pudhipithan, Short Stories, Novels, Plays, Biographies, Essays and research works (Thesis)".

While this method of tabulation and arrangements is widely acceptable, new tabulation methodologies shall be postulated keeping the library situations would add feasibility.

Influence of Updating Natrinai

Wiki source serves as a platform of sources strengthening educational sources, thus enabling Tamil natural and language related research. Despite this, Wiki source facilitates it as a library for Scholars from across the globe from different universities to undertake their research works. Also, the positive impact of Wiki source are,

- Enables research work to bloom continuously on Natrinai
- Enable research on comparative literature of Indian language to strive in a smoother phase.
- Smooth conduct of comparative literature of Global languages.
- Fetch data for research on the Nature of Languages.
- Usage of words from Natrinai in the schemes of Wiktionary.
- Enriching the data Wiki medium.
- Create new essays in Wikipedia.
- Instrument data distribution from Natrinai.
- Creating new software related to Natrinai.

- Instrumentation on Natrinai learning and Teaching platforms.

Conclusion

Ancient Tamil words strive as the treasure of Ancient Tamil Literature. Ancestors have safeguarded it from two thousand years of invasions, genocides and technological advancements and preserved it to the present day. Updating these resources in digital medium and chiefly in Wiki source would be an analogy to preservation in a safety wallet. This purpose shall be served by updating the above furnished books to Wiki source and improving the data on Natrinai.

Hence from all these explanations, one can conclude that the researches scattered on different places with Natrinai as its base shall be brought under one roof – Tamil Wiki source, which acts as the Treasured Library. When this takes shape, Tamil Wiki source shall be the fore runner among the 72 other Wiki source schemes. It is evident that with History of Tamil literature as a basis, will pave the way for the growth of Wiki source.

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